

**Circular
Cities & Regions
Initiative**

Knowledge Hub

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project Management Handbook/D1.1

WP 1, T 1.1 and T.1.4

Authors: Mireia Ferri, Alba Matamoros (KVC); Carlos Serra (UEG)

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This project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON EU research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101135174. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Technical references

Project Acronym	CCRI-KH
Project Title	Knowledge hub to leverage existing initiatives and projects to foster the adoption of Circular economy in Cities and Regions in Europe
Project Coordinator	Kveloce ccriknowledgehub@kveloce.com
Project Duration	January 2024 – December 2026 (36 months)

Deliverable No.	D1.1
Dissemination level*	PU
Work Package	WP 1 - Project Management and Network coordination
Task	T1.1 - Project management T1.4 - Internal evaluation, quality control & risk management
Lead beneficiary	1 (KVC)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	8 (UVEG)
Due date of deliverable	31st March 2025
Actual submission date	28th March 2025

- *PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)
- SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444
- Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

v	Date	Beneficiary	Author
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0.1	21/02/2024	Kveloce	Alba Matamoros, Mireia Ferri
0.2	27/02/2024	UVEG	Carlos serra
0.3-0.5	04/03/2024	Kveloce	Alba Matamoros, Mireia Ferri
0.5	20/03/2024	KFL	Kamil Maszczyk
0.5	26/03/2024	CETEC	Enya López Sánchez
1.0	29/03/2024	Kveloce	Alba Matamoros, Mireia Ferri
2.0	13/06/2024	Kveloce	Lorena Aguilar
3.0	14/02/2025	Kveloce	Cristina Vera, Alba Matamoros
3.0	15/02/2025	UVEG, CETEC, KFL	Carlos Serra, Ana Crespo, Kamil Maszczyk
4.0	28/03/2025	Kveloce	Alba Matamoros

Table of contents

Table of contents	4
0. Introduction.....	7
0.1. Project Overview.....	7
0.2. Delivery Purpose & Scope.....	10
0.3. Target Audience	11
0.4. Applicable documents	11
0.5. Acronyms	11
1. Management structure – responsibilities and roles	13
1.1. General Assembly (GA).....	13
1.2. Project Management Board (PMB)	14
1.3. Project Coordinator (PC)	14
1.4. Technical Coordinator (TC)	15
1.5. External bodies	15
1.5.1. European Commission (EC)	15
1.5.2. CCRI & CCRI-CSO agents	16
2. Operational level	17
2.1. WP leaders and task leaders	17
2.2. Responsibilities of each partner	17
2.3. Decision making process, conflict resolution & change management	18
2.3.1. Decision making process.....	18
2.3.2. Conflict resolution	18
2.3.3. Changes management.....	19
3. Consortium communication	22
3.1. Communication with the EC	22
3.2. Communication with L1, L2 & L3	22
3.3. Internal communication	22
3.3.1. Emails and mailing lists	22
3.3.2. Shared calendar.....	24
3.3.3. Teams channel	24
3.3.4. Meetings.....	25
3.4. External communication	31
3.4.1. Dissemination strategy	31
3.4.2. Visual identity	31
4. Document management	33
4.1. Online Project repository folder	33
4.1.1. Project Deliverables & Milestones	34
4.1.2. Documents.....	34

4.2. Deliverables	36
4.2.1. Templates	39
4.2.2. Deliverable Status Information	39
4.2.3. Naming Conventions and Versioning	39
4.2.4. Tracking of Changes and Commenting.....	39
4.2.5. Roles and responsibilities	40
4.2.6. EU Response to deliverables	40
5. Quality management.....	41
5.1. Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) in CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB ..	43
5.1.1. QA: methods, means and phases	43
5.1.2. QC Procedure and reporting.....	44
6. Risk management	52
6.1. RMCP Procedures	53
7. Monitoring project performance	55
7.1. Periodic Reports	55
7.2. Internal Project Monitoring.....	55
7.2.1. Planning: WP three term plans	56
7.2.2. Reporting: WP internally reports	56
7.3. Administrative and financial coordination.....	57
7.3.1. Internal Justification M12	57
7.3.2. First Report Justification M18	57
7.3.3. Final Report Justification M36	57
7.3.4. Useful resources	58
8. Annexes	59
8.1. Distribution of deliverable reviewers	59
8.2. Change Log template	61
8.3. WP internally quarterly report – template.....	63
8.4. Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire	71
8.5. Checklist for scientific dissemination outputs	76
8.6. Transnational Meeting Quality Evaluation Questionnaire	77
8.7. Internal Evaluation Survey for the project internal quality	79

List of Tables

Table 1 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Work Packages, resources & deliverables.	8
Table 2 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB milestones.....	9
Table 3 - General Assembly (GA).....	13
Table 4 - Project Management Board (PMB)	14
Table 5 - Project Coordinator (PC).....	14
Table 6 - Technical Coordinator (TC)	15
Table 7 - European Commission (EC)	15
Table 8 - 1.5.2. CCRI & CCRI-CSO agents	16

Table 9 - Monthly consortium meetings.....	26
Table 10 - Monthly L1 online meetings	27
Table 11 - Monthly PMB meetings	28
Table 12 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB face-to-face meetings.....	29
Table 13 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB deliverables list	36
Table 14 - Distribution of deliverable reviewers	59
Table 15 - Change Log template	61
Table 16 - Aims & Objectives of activities undertaken during the Quarter	63
Table 17 - Activities undertaken & partners involved during the reporting period	64
Table 18 - Issues arising during the quarter.....	66
Table 19 - Risk Identification and analysis (WP Milestone Status).....	68
Table 20 - Project Deliverables Status	68
Table 21 - Project Deliverables Status	69
Table 22 - Resources consumption monitoring	70
Table 23 - Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire (Section 1)	71
Table 24 - Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire (Section 2)	72
Table 25 - Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire (Section 3)	73
Table 26 - Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire (Section 4)	73
Table 27 - Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire (Section 5)	76
Table 28 - Checklist for scientific dissemination outputs	76
Table 29 - Transnational Meeting Quality Evaluation Questionnaire	77
Table 30 - Internal Evaluation Survey for the project internal quality	79

List of Figures

Figure 1 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB 's formula	7
Figure 2 - Operational management communication	17
Figure 3 - QM key concepts	42

List of Images

Image 1 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Calendar SharePoint.....	24
Image 2 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Teams Channel SharePoint	24
Image 3 CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB SharePoint.....	33
Image 4 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB : Project deliverables & milestones SharePoint	34
Image 5 - Reporting procedure	55

0. Introduction

0.1. Project Overview

CCRI Knowledge Hub aims at increasing the impact of the existing Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) by enlarging the network of involved stakeholders, bringing together the knowledge and critical mass already developed around Circular Economy implementation and building upon the Circular Economy stakeholder platform. The goal is to promote and make the circular economy concept a reality in EU cities and regions, in particular in those in the early stage of circular economy transition. To reach its objective, CCRI Knowledge Hub will act as a “Knowledge Hub”, leveraging existing initiatives and projects to foster the adoption of circular economy in EU cities and regions. CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB ´s formula is based on three principles: (a) easy access to systematised workable knowledge; (b) tailored mentoring according to users’ needs and (c) effective awareness-raising to make the circular economy more desirable, that build upon four main

Figure 1 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB 's formula

dimensions: (i) Public engagement; (ii) Innovation and technology; (iii) Business models and financial support; and (iv) Impact evaluation. CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB gathers a multidisciplinary expert consortium of 11 partners from 6 EU countries (research and technological centres, universities, research organisations, international networks and associations, regional authorities as well as specialised companies and SMEs) that bring in complementary skills and competences to achieve the project ´s objectives.

Project basic data:

- Starting date: 1st of January 2024
- Closing date: 31st of December 2026

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- Duration: 36 months.
- Maximum grant amount (as stated in the annex 2 of the Grant Agreement): 2.612.932,04€.
- Project number: 101135174
- Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-CircBio-01-1
- Type of action: Coordination and Support Action (CSA)

In the following tables (Table 1 & Table 2) a summary of the project work packages (WP) is shown, together with other relevant information linked with them as well as a summary of the project milestones, considering the whole project duration (36 months):

Table 1 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Work Packages, resources & deliverables.

WPN ^o	Title	Lead partner	PM	Start- End month	Deliverables
WP1	Project Management and Network coordination – 1	1 - KVC	23.50	1-18	D1.1 – Project Management Handbook-1 D1.2 – Network Coordination Guidelines-1 D1.3 – Ethics and Data Management Plan-1 D1.4 – Clustering activities-1
WP2	Knowledge and Resource Building	2 - CETEC	54.00	1-18	D2.1 – CE projects/initiatives, GPs & less successful cases D2.2 – Resources compilation to support a successful transition to a circular economy in cities/regions (Folder with materials, tools and resources)
WP3	Preparation of customised support services, capacity building and first delivery of services	8 - UVEG	47.00	1-18	D3.1 – CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Support Pathways D3.2 – On-line repository of resources, including the database /catalogue of sectoral/cross-sectoral technologies that facilitate circularity D3.3 – Delivery of first services (1st 18 months of the project)

					D3.4 – Mentoring Guide
WP4	Dissemination & Communication- 1	6 - ICONS	34.00	1-18	D4.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy D4.2 – D&C activities and impact analysis-1 D4.3 – Community building.
WP5	Project Management and Network coordination-2	1 - KVC	21.50	19-36	D5.1 – Network Coordination Guidelines -2 D5.2 – Project Management Handbook-2 D5.3 – Ethics and Data Management Plan-2 D5.4 – Clustering activities-2
WP6	Delivery of Customized support services and capacity building and continuous knowledge building updating/finetuning	8 - UVEG	69.50	19-36	D6.1 – Delivery of services (2nd 18 months of the project)
WP7	Dissemination, Communication-2	6 - ICONS	41.00	19-36	D7.1 – Dissemination and Communication Strategy-2 (Update) D7.2 – D&C activities and impact analysis-2 D7.3 – Community building-2
WP8	Policy recommendations and Sustainability	11 - ALDA	38.00	19-36	D8.1 – Exploitation and sustainability strategy D8.2 – Policy recommendations and lessons learnt

Table 2 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB milestones

M No.	Milestone name	WP(s)	Due date	Means of verification/controller (verified by)
M1	Guidelines/protocols for info gathering and analysis	WP2	M3	The templates and the guidelines/protocols to gather the information developed under Task 2.1 are being used by partners. WP Leader will acknowledge the reception of it. / PC (KVC) & WP Leader (CETEC)

M2	Planning of the activities to be carried out during the first 18 months of the project (M1-M18).	WP3	M4	Planning document detailing all the activities carried out during the first 18 months of the project will be released to the partners. Partner will acknowledge the reception of the plan/ Coordination Team (KVC+CETEC)
M3	Decision on where to incorporate the platform taken and beta- version CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB platform released	WP2	M6	Platform set-up, in terms of it is working, and also a validation from the rest of the partners will be asked. Coordination Team (KVC+CETEC)
M4	Mentors identified and engaged.	WP3	M18	Mentors' contracts signed. The contract details their duties within KCCRI project. / PC (KVC)
M5	Planning of the activities to be carried out during the second 18 months of the project (M19-M36).	WP6	M21	Planning document released. detailing all the activities carried out during the second 18 months of the project will be released to the partners. Partner will acknowledge the reception of the plan / Coordination Team (KVC+CETEC)
M6	CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Platform ready with online repository.	WP6	M24	Platform running and in use. To have a feedback from one user. / Coordination Team (KVC+CETEC)
M7	Individual/personalized Mentoring Plans	WP6	M30	Plans for >75% mentees drafted/ Coordination Team (KVC+CETEC)
M8	Focus groups/open consultations with stakeholders carried out.	WP8	M33	Attendance/participation list of the stakeholders in the focus groups and open consultations/ Project Coordinator (KVC)

0.2. Delivery Purpose & Scope

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide project partners with an easy-to-use, friendly manual for all project procedures and communications. This document provides the foundation for the practical work in the project throughout its duration and will help to ensure that all project partners will follow the same well-defined procedures and practices. Thus, this deliverable is an important and mandatory tool to ensure that the project is delivered on specification, on time, and on budget.

This document contains a description of the following aspects:

- management structure, description, operation, responsibilities and roles of each management body;

- guidelines for the different necessary communication tasks stemming from the progress of the project: communication with the European Commission (EC), internal communication within the Consortium and external communication, that is communication to society in general and dissemination;
- tools, creation, management and official delivery of project documentation;
- process of internal quality review for deliverables and other scientific and dissemination outputs;
- and reporting activities.

Although formally delivered at Month 15, the Project Handbook is, a “**living document**”, thus, its content may be adapted through the project duration to reflect changes within the project management procedures.

0.3. Target Audience

This document is listed in the Description of Action (DoA) as “public”. It aims to provide crucial information to project participants, guiding them on various aspects of project management and procedures. Secondly, it fulfils a requirement outlined in the DoA, indicating its intended accessibility to a wider audience, including the EC and appointed independent expert reviewers. By being publicly accessible, it ensures transparency and accountability, allowing stakeholders to gain insights into the project's management approach and procedures.

0.4. Applicable documents

The following documents have been necessary to develop the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB project management guideline and quality plan:

- CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB DoA, which is Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement Number 101135174 and contains the details of how the action (project) will be carried out. This document was prepared during the initiating and planning phase of the project.
- CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Grant Agreement number 101135174.
- CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Consortium agreement (CA).
- PM² Project Management Methodology Guide 3.0.1, March 2021.
- PM² Glossary based on the PM² Guide v3.0

0.5. Acronyms

ALDA: ALDA - ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE POUR LA DEMOCRATIE LOCALE

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CA: Consortium Agreement
CCRI: Circular cities and regions initiative
CCRI-CSO: Circular cities and regions initiative coordination & support office
CETEC: Asociación Empresarial de Investigación, centro tecnológico del calzado y del plástico de la Región de Murcia
DOA: Description of Action
EBN: European Business and Innovation Centre Network AISBL
EC: European Commission
EU: European Union
EURADA: Association Europeenne des Agencesde Developpement
FILSE: Finanziaria Ligure per lo Sviluppoeconomic FI.L.S.E. SPA
FPO: Financial Project Officer
GA: General Assembly
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation
ICONS: Fondazione ICONS
INV: Cartago Ventures SL
KFL: K-FLEX POLSKA Sp z o.o.
KPI: Key Performance Indicator
KVC: Kveloce
PC: Project Coordinator
PMB: Project Management Board
PO: Project Officer
PR: Periodic Reports
QA: Quality Assurance
QC: Quality Control
QM: Quality Management
REA: Research Executive Agency
RMCP: Risk Management and Contingency Plan
TC: Technical Coordinator
TPM: Transnational Project Meeting
UVEG: Universitat de València
VTT: Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY
WP: Work Package
WPL: Work Package Leader
WPMT: WP Management Teams

1. Management structure – responsibilities and roles

The management structure aims at safeguarding the effective governance of the project, with special focus on the cooperation among the members of the Consortium and on the production of high-quality deliverables to the EC and interested stakeholders, mainly to the CCRI community, during the duration of the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB project.

1.1. General Assembly (GA)

Table 3 - General Assembly (GA)

WHAT 	<p>The GA is the strategic decision-making body of the consortium. Main issues:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agree all the key decisions concerning the project; • Agree activity plans and the budget; • Provide liaison between relevant stakeholders, establishing any necessary contacts required; • Approving the project plan and any changes of the plan; • Deciding on the procedures, operational rules, technologies and standards to adopt in the project; and • Proposing recommendations and directions to improve the project management.
WHO 	<p>Chaired by PC and one representative per partner¹</p>
HOW 	<p>All decisions of the GA are taken with 2/3 majority votes. The quorum of the GA meetings is 2/3 of its members.</p>
WHERE & WHEN 	<p>The GA will take the format of physical meeting. Provisional Calendar:</p> <p>Month – Host (City-Country)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. January 2024 (M1) Kick-Off Meeting – KVC (Brussels-BE) 2. June 2024 (M6) – ICONS (Milan, IT) 3. November 2024 (M11) – EURADA (Brussels, BE) 4. June 2025 (M18) – VTT (Espoo, FI) 5. December 2025 (M24)– CETEC (Murcia, ES)

¹ Each General Assembly Member shall be deemed to be duly authorised to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters listed in Section 6.3.1.2 of the CA.

- 6. June 2026 (M30) – ALDA (Strasbourg, FR)
- 7. December 2026 (M36) – KVC (Brussels, BE)

1.2. Project Management Board (PMB)

Table 4 - Project Management Board (PMB)

WHAT 	<p>The PMB main tasks are the following (more information can be found on the CA):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the GA; • Monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the project; • Collect information at least every 3 months on the progress of the project, examine that information to assess the compliance of the project with the DoA and, if necessary, propose modifications to the GA; and • Support the PC in preparing meetings with the Granting Authority and in preparing related data and deliverables.
WHO 	<p>The PMB shall consist of the PC and the representatives of the WP leaders.</p>
WHERE & WHEN 	<p>At least quarterly, after the Internal Progress Report presentation. Meetings of the PMB are usually held by tele- or videoconference or other telecommunication means, unless they are held the same date as the face-to-face GA meetings.</p>

1.3. Project Coordinator (PC)

Table 5 - Project Coordinator (PC)

WHAT 	<p>The PC shall be responsible of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitoring and ensuring compliance with obligations from Consortium and Grant Agreements; • Maintaining updated contact information for members; • Managing and submitting reports, financial statements, and requested documents to the Granting Authority; and • Organising and facilitating meetings, including preparing agendas, chairing meetings, and ensuring implementation of decisions.
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WHO 	SENIOR EUROPA S.L (Kveloce). The PC as the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority. The PC shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and in the CA.
WHERE & WHEN 	At any time upon request of any Member of the PMB

1.4. Technical Coordinator (TC)

Table 6 - Technical Coordinator (TC)

WHAT 	The TC will be in charge of managing and monitoring the technical activities to ensure the proper implementation of the planned tasks and the appropriate methodology of the research carried out by the partners during the project.
WHO 	CETEC, a Technological Center with a long trajectory in the footwear and plastics areas and very active in circular economy, is the TC.
WHERE & WHEN 	At any time upon request of any Member of the PMB

1.5. External bodies

1.5.1. European Commission (EC)

Table 7 - European Commission (EC)

WHAT 	The EC is the funding authority of CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB. Their role is based on the following activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow up the grant agreement; • Advising on project problems, changes, etc.; • Guidance on Grant Agreement amendments, if any; • Assessment of periodic reports and deliverables; and • Order interim and final payments.
WHO 	The EC has appointed two contact persons to follow up the progress of the project: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Officer (PO): • Financial Project Officer (FPO):

	Besides, the EC appoints expert reviewers who assist them in assessment of the deliverables and technical reports. The name of reviewers is disclosed before the review meeting and PC, on behalf of the Consortium, may request the dismissal of the suggested reviewers based on objective reasons (conflict of interest with any Beneficiary, for instance).
WHERE & WHEN 	<p>Regular communications between EC and CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB are done through emails and videocalls. They are also invited to participate in transnational project meetings and in monthly project meetings.</p> <p>Official communications are channelled through Participant Portal (always done by the PC).</p>

1.5.2. CCRI & CCRI-CSO agents

Table 8 - 1.5.2. CCRI & CCRI-CSO agents

WHAT 	<p>The first level of collaboration, coordination & cooperation between CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB, CCRI and CCRI-CSO has as purpose to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the alignment of goals; • Shared planning; • Information exchange; • Ongoing communication; • Ensure complementarity of activities & avoid duplication; • Cooperative logistics; • Identify potential risks & mitigation measures; and • Ensure participation in CCRI events.
WHO 	<p>CCRI managing structure (Directorate-General for research and innovation) & Coordination & support office (Ecorys)</p>
WHERE & WHEN 	<p>Regular communications between CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB, CCRI and CCRI-CSO is planned through:</p> <p>Periodic meetings: 1 monthly meeting (online or face-to-face). Review meetings: every 6 months (face-to-face). Meetings on demand: whenever necessary.</p>

2. Operational level

2.1. WP leaders and task leaders

The WPL and Task Leaders are tasked with the operational management of the research, development and implementation of activities that need to be undertaken within their respective WP or Task. Task Leaders report directly to their corresponding WPL and suggest appropriate methodologies and strategies to ensure an efficient progress of the WP outcomes. WP and Task Leaders are the immediate contact person for all queries regarding activities in the project, as seen in :

Figure 2 - Operational management communication

2.2. Responsibilities of each partner

ART. 11.1 of Grant Agreement and Part 4 of the CA covers the general responsibilities of the beneficiaries. In general terms *“The beneficiaries must implement the action as described in Annex 1 and in compliance with the provisions of the Agreement, the call conditions and all legal obligations under applicable EU, international and national law”*.

In the frame of these documents, here are listed some specific responsibilities:

1. Partners are required to read the project CA and Grant Agreement (available at the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB shared internal repository and also on SyGMa).
2. For any problem with SyGMa (access, name changes, etc), please contact both the PC and the EU HelpDesk or your national contact point.
3. Please keep every official project communication (e.g. emails) in English.
4. In case of problems or doubts, do raise the issue as early as possible!
5. It is the partners’ responsibility to take into account the schedule of deliverables when establishing the planning.
6. Each partner should ensure to respond to e-mail within 3 workdays.
7. Each partner should ensure to designate a back-up within his/her organisation in case of absence or limited availability.

8. The PC would request partners to be on standby when the Annual Report needs to be submitted.
9. Partners remain responsible for keeping track of/ reporting expenses and time.
10. Partners will notify any change in the company/institution legally responsible or composition.

2.3. Decision making process, conflict resolution & change management

2.3.1. Decision making process

The decision making has a hierarchy of 'instruments' broadly as follows:

DECISIONS HIERARCHY: Partner → Task Leader → WPL → PMB → PC → GA

DOCUMENT HIERARCHY: CA → DoA → Grant Agreement

However, each body has a right to subsidiarity (self-control and decision making at the lowest level) if it does not conflict with decisions/procedures/agreements of an 'upper' 'instrument'.

2.3.2. Conflict resolution

The WP Leaders will be responsible for operational decisions within their respective WP, while the GA will oversee decisions pertaining to the project's strategic development. Conflict resolution will follow a five-step procedure:

Step 1: Problem-solving discussions and negotiations will typically occur during ordinary and ad-hoc meetings among relevant partners.

Step 2: If a solution cannot be reached, the concerned partners will notify the WP Leader, who will mediate between them.

Step 3: If resolution remains elusive, the WP Leader will escalate the matter to the PC, who will facilitate mediation.

Step 4: If resolution remains unattainable, the GA will convene an extraordinary meeting within 15 days.

Step 5: If the conflict persists or significantly impacts the project's viability or scope, the PC will seek guidance from the EC Project Officers.

In severe cases, the PC may recommend external mediation, jointly funded by the conflicting parties.

Quorum: The GA shall not decide on issues unless two-thirds (2/3) of its members are present or represented (including attendees joining by teleconference)².

- Each of the Beneficiaries has one vote. Absent members are not entitled to vote or transfer votes.
- Decisions will be taken by a simple majority of votes with the Project Coordinator holding a casting vote in the event of a tie.
- All partners retain a veto right.

2.3.3. Changes management

The project change management process defines the activities related to **identifying, documenting, assessing, approving, prioritising, planning and controlling** changes, and communicating them to the GA. The change management process for this project is a five-step process and falls under the responsibilities of the PC who should execute the process when required throughout the project lifecycle.

Step 1: Change Identification:

The aim of this step is to streamline the process of identifying and documenting change requests to project baselines, encompassing scope, requirements, deliverables, resources, costs, schedule, or quality characteristics. Changes can be requested (or identified and raised) throughout the project lifecycle by any member of the Consortium. After receiving a change request, the PC registers the requested change in the Change Log and makes sure the change request is described using the Change Request Form (Change Log template). A request for a change can be submitted formally via a Change Request Form or can be identified and raised during meetings as a result of decisions, issues or risks. The Change Log contains information as the change identifier, the name of the requestor, the date of identification, the change category (e.g. new requirement, issue or risk related, business, etc.), the change details and impact, and the status of the change.

Step 2: Change Assessment and Action Recommendation:

The purpose of this step is to assess:

- a) whether this request is indeed a project change;

² Information included in the Consortium Agreement

- b) to define the different options to meet this request;
- c) to assess the size of the identified change for each option defined in terms of the impact to the project objectives, quality, risk, schedule, cost, effort, and the contract with the contractor;
- d) to decide on a priority for the implementation of that change request.

After this assessment, the recommended action will be detailed with the necessary steps, deliverables, cost, timescale and resources involved. Be aware that the recommended action may be to reject the requested change. This information will be documented by the PC in the Change Log tracker, which is then used as an input to the formal change approval or rejection by the appropriate decision makers. New changes can generate new risks, issues or quality requirements and therefore change assessment will include the assessment of current or new risks, issues and quality requirements. The design of the change implementation (action) will also impact cost, scheduling and resources assigned to the project, so all these dimensions will be assessed before change approval. It is important to bear in mind that a change may require an amendment that implies a considerable amount of administrative work that is costly and may delay the project.

Step 3: Change Approval

The purpose of this step is to achieve a decision regarding the approval or rejection of the change. Changes classified with high size will always be communicated to the PO. There are four possible decisions to be considered: Approve, Reject, Postpone, or Merge the change request. The decision details are documented in the Change Log. If the change request needs further information or clarification, it returns to the "Change Assessment and Action Recommendation" step.

Step 4: Change Implementation

For the approved or merged changes, the WP leaders will incorporate the actions related to these changes into the WP annual work plans and update project related documentation.

Step 5: Change Control

The purpose of this step is to monitor and control project changes, to be able to easily communicate them to the several decision layers of the project, for approval or status updates. The PC will collect any changes to the project or related actions and control the status of each change management activity.

WP meetings will be used to revise the status of changes and related actions, and to identify new changes. The PC is responsible for updating the Change Log tracker, which can include adding new changes, updating change status, updating effort estimation, modifying size and/or priority levels based on changes in project environment, etc. Additionally, the PC will report periodically (quarterly) the status of project changes to the PMB and, when adequate, to other project participants.

3. Consortium communication

This Section provides with guidelines for the different necessary communication tasks stemming from the progress of the project: communication with the EC, communication with the three levels of collaboration, coordination and cooperation, internal communication within the Consortium and external communication, that is communication to society in general and dissemination.

3.1. Communication with the EC

Concerning communication with the EC, the PC will be the unique communication channel (except in circumstances explicitly defined in the Grant Agreement/CA) to unify and facilitate the communication procedures. This way, the PO and other officers at the EC will be provided with a unique contact.

3.2. Communication with L1, L2 & L3

CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB has the coordination in its core. The way CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB bring together the three levels of coordination is reported in *D.1.2. Network Coordination Guidelines-1*.

3.3. Internal communication

The main tools and channels for internal communication with the Consortium, among partners are explained in the following subsections.

3.3.1. Emails and mailing lists

Email is currently the main communication tool for collaboration within geographically distributed teams. Some important recommendations to be followed within the project are:

- In general, partners should avoid massive and unnecessary emails.

- To facilitate effective and efficient communication an excel contact sheet has been created and stored at the common repository (*name of the tool: KCCRI_Contact_data.xls | SharePoint*). This contact list includes the contact data of the persons from each partner, that are going to participate or have a role in the different tasks of the project. **In case there are changes during the project, partners must communicate them to the PC and provide the new contact(s)**. The different roles of the persons participating in the project are also included.
- In the subject line of the email the name of the project & the related WP must be indicated in brackets as **[CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB | WP1]** followed by the main issue of the email.
- When the email includes information about deadlines, it must be highlighted and have to be adhered to firmly. In case that a certain deadline cannot be met by a participant, this has to be communicated in time to the WPL and the PC.
- In case that someone might not be able to access to email for some period of time (e.g., due to vacation), an automatic reply has to be configured so that the senders of emails are notified about the possibility that their email will be read at a later time.
- Try to avoid attaching files to emails, especially when they are too large. Instead, upload the files to the appropriate SharePoint folders and include a link to the uploaded file in the email rather than attaching the document itself. This approach is also beneficial when collaborating on documents; provide contributors with a link to the document uploaded in SharePoint, and the file owner will grant them access to edit it, following the recommendations outlined in Subsection 4.2.2.

3.3.2. Shared calendar

SharePoint gives the option of creating a shared calendar to be managed by the users of the

Image 1 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Calendar | SharePoint

This calendar is a tool to be used by all the partners to share common interesting events and to include internal deadlines and meetings. A colour code has been created to include the

different activities of the project:

- **Red:** internal deadlines, such as deliverables submission, end of revision periods...
- **Yellow:** events organised outside the consortium (external events).
- **Green:** internal meetings.
- **Orange:** events organised by the consortium (internal events).

If a relevant event is identified, it must be notified to the consortium, not only by including it in the shared calendar, but also by email or posting it on the Teams channel.

3.3.3. Teams channel

Teams channel will be used only as a tool to communicate certain reminders or concrete

Image 2 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Teams Channel | SharePoint

actions (voting on a poll, reviewing some document...).

The main communication tool will be email.

3.3.4. Meetings

Common rules

Online project meetings will be organised using Teams as the main tool. They can be recorded, always with GDPR compliance. Each chairperson is responsible for sending the link to join and the call invitation to the required participants. For the in-person meetings, it is established in the DoA the partner hosting the meeting, and therefore, responsible to the related logistics. For these meetings, the PC will support the hosting partner drafting the agenda, send the needed reminders, etc.

All kind of project meetings, online or physical ones, should follow a set of minimum recommendations for their preparation and management.

As for the preparation of meetings:

- The chairperson should include both a notice and an appropriate agenda to each member as soon as possible, according to the reached agreement.
- The meeting notice should clearly identify the objectives of the meeting and allow adjusting them in dialog within a certain timeframe. It should also identify partners expected to attend explicitly by specifying both mandatory and optional cases.
- The date and time of the meeting can be specified using modern voting portals (Doodle, Microsoft Forms); in case of recurring meetings, however, it is recommended to agree on the date and time of the next meeting during each meeting, as far as possible.

Good practices for the duration of a meeting are:

- To increase chances for achieving meeting goals within the scheduled timeframes, participants should join before the scheduled start time.
- A second person other than the chairperson should keep the time and give appropriate notifications.
- A note-taker should be specified.

There should be minutes after each meeting. The minutes must highlight the agenda, the summary of discussions, such as action points (including what, who and when information) and agreements reached during the meeting. If the document becomes too long, a summary of the highlights must be included in the beginning of the minutes.

The draft of the meeting minutes will be sent to the Members of the Consortium no later than 10 calendar days after the meeting. Minutes will be considered accepted if the Members send no objection to the minutes within 15 calendar days from sending the minutes. Minutes will not be additionally sent out but will be readily available without undue delay in SharePoint.

Monthly Consortium Conference calls

Place: Online (teams)

Duration: 1h 30'

Day and time: the second Monday of every month from 11.30 to 13.00 pm (see Table 93 below).

Content:

- Key issues to deal with at the stage of the project:
 - Accomplishments (current and planned actions);
 - Plans reviews;
 - Actual work vs. planned;
 - Milestone status;
 - Risks identification, assessment and response;
 - Arising issues; and
 - Results & dissemination activities.
- WP leaders report activity
- Joint activities & events planed for the following month

Note take responsible: PC

Provisional calendar for Monthly online Consortium meetings till June 2025³ (*NOTE: all the meetings are already scheduled and included in the project shared calendar*):

Table 9 - Monthly consortium meetings

Monthly Consortium meetings <i>(subject to change if needed)</i>	
March 2024	Monday 11 th form 11:30 to 13:00
April 2024	Monday 8 th form 11:30 to 13:00
May 2024	Monday 13 th form 11:30 to 13:00
June 2024	Monday 10 th form 11:30 to 13:00
July 2024	Monday 8 th form 11:30 to 13:00
August 2024	Monday 12 th form 11:30 to 13:00
September 2024	Monday 9 th form 11:30 to 13:00
October 2024	Monday 14 th form 11:30 to 13:00

³ Meetings from June 2025 to December 2026 will be included in the second period of the project

November 2024	Monday 11 th form 11:30 to 13:00
December 2024	Monday 9 th form 11:30 to 13:00
January 2025	Monday 13 th form 11:30 to 13:00
February 2025	Monday 10 th form 11:30 to 13:00
March 2025	Monday 10 th form 11:30 to 13:00
April 2025	Monday 14 th form 11:30 to 13:00
May 2025	Monday 12 th form 11:30 to 13:00
June 2025	Monday 9 th form 11:30 to 13:00

Monthly L1 Conference calls

Place: Online (teams)

Duration: 1h

Day and time: After the monthly online consortium meetings, every month the second Monday of the month from 14.00 to 15.00.

Content: All the information regarding this meeting can be found on deliverable *D.1.2. Network Coordination Guidelines-1*.

Note take responsible: PC.

Table 10 - Monthly L1 online meetings

Monthly L1 meetings (<i>subject to change if needed</i>)	
March 2024	Monday 11 th form 14.00 to 15.00
April 2024	Monday 8 th form 14.00 to 15.00
May 2024	Monday 13 th form 14.00 to 15.00
June 2024	Monday 10 th form 14.00 to 15.00
July 2024	Monday 8 th form 14.00 to 15.00
August 2024	Monday 12 th form 14.00 to 15.00
September 2024	Monday 9 th form 14.00 to 15.00
October 2024	Monday 14 th form 14.00 to 15.00
November 2024	Monday 11 th form 14.00 to 15.00
December 2024	Monday 9 th form 14.00 to 15.00
January 2025	Monday 13 th form 14.00 to 15.00
February 2025	Monday 10 th form 14.00 to 15.00
March 2025	Monday 10 th form 14.00 to 15.00
April 2025	Monday 14 th form 14.00 to 15.00
May 2025	Monday 12 th form 14.00 to 15.00
June 2025	Monday 9 th form 14.00 to 15.00

Monthly PMB Conference calls

Place: Online (teams)

Duration: 1h

Day and time: the first Thursday of every month from 13.00 to 14.00 pm (see **Error! Reference source not found.5**)

Funded by
the European Union

Content: The aim of these meetings is to discuss any arising issues and to assess the individual and overall implementation of the project, as well as, to prepare the monthly consortium meetings and the meetings with L1 of coordination.

Note take responsible: each WP leader is responsible for taking notes and sending them to the PC. A shared document to work on the minutes will be distributed among participants and is responsibility of each WPL to complete their slot.

Provisional calendar for monthly online PMB meetings till June 2025⁴ (*NOTE: all the meetings are already scheduled and included in the project shared calendar*):

Table 11 - Monthly PMB meetings

Monthly PMB meetings (<i>subject to change if needed</i>)	
March 2024	Thursday 7 th form 13.00 to 14.00
April 2024	Thursday 4 th form 13.00 to 14.00
May 2024	Thursday 2 nd form 13.00 to 14.00
June 2024	Thursday 6 th form 13.00 to 14.00
July 2024	Thursday 4 th form 13.00 to 14.00
August 2024	Thursday 1 st form 13.00 to 14.00
September 2024	Thursday 5 th form 13.00 to 14.00
October 2024	Thursday 3 rd form 13.00 to 14.00
November 2024	Thursday 7 th form 13.00 to 14.00
December 2024	Thursday 5 th form 13.00 to 14.00
January 2025	Thursday 2 nd form 13.00 to 14.00
February 2025	Thursday 6 th form 13.00 to 14.00
March 2025	Thursday 6 th form 13.00 to 14.00
April 2025	Thursday 3 rd form 13.00 to 14.00
May 2025	Thursday 1 st form 13.00 to 14.00
June 2025	Thursday 5 th form 13.00 to 14.00

Transnational Project Meetings

Place and timeline: 7 face-to face periodic meetings at partner countries. The Kick-off Meeting, plus 2 meetings per year during the project. Estimated face-to-face consortium meetings are detailed in Table 12:

⁴ Meetings from June 2025 to December 2026 will be included in the second period of the project

Table 12 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB face-to-face meetings

Event	Partner Responsible	Location
Kick Off Meeting (January 2024) (✓)	Kveloce	Brussels, BELGIUM
M6 (June 2024) (✓)	ICONS	Milan, ITALY
M11 (November 2024) ⁵ (✓)	EURADA	Brussels, BELGIUM
M18 (June 2025) ⁶	VTT	Espoo, FINLAND
M24 (December 2025)	CETEC	Murcia, SPAIN
M30 (June 2026)	ALDA	Strasbourg, FRANCE
M36 – Final event (December 2026)	Kveloce	Brussels, BELGIUM

Duration: 2 days meeting

Content: Monitoring of the tasks done and to be done in the next 6 months in each live WP, and according to the project timeline relevant issues of each WP will be discussed, fostering participatory activities.

Note take responsible: each WPL is responsible for taking notes and sending them to the PC. A shared document to work on the minutes will be distributed among participants and is responsibility of each WPL to complete their slot.

Social dinner management: each partner will cover their own expenses. It is not mandatory for the host institution to cover dinner expenses; however, if the host institution wishes, they may choose to do so⁷.

⁵ NOTE: this meeting shall be organised in November instead of December to match with the European Circular Week.

⁶ NOTE: the project meeting planned for the month 24 (December 25) in Finland will be swapped with either the meeting planned in Spain (month 18) OR France (month 30) to optimize logistics. This involves only a change in the scheduled meeting locations over time; however, all hosting partners and the number of meetings remain the same.

⁷ Please, keep in mind that these expenses are not covered by the European funding.

GA Meetings

The GA will meet twice a year in ordinary meeting⁸, and also at any time upon written request of the PMB or 1/3 of the Members of the GA, as extraordinary meeting.

Section 6 of CA regulates aspects concerning its operation, such as:

- Members have to be notified in writing as soon as possible and no later than 45 calendar days for ordinary meeting and 15 calendar days for Extraordinary meeting;
- The agenda must be prepared and sent to each Member no later than 21 calendar days, 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting;
- Any Member may add an item to the original agenda by written notification to all of the other Members of GA up to 14 calendar days before the meeting, 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting;
- Partners must confirm their attendance to plenary meetings;
- There will be written minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. Draft minutes will be sent to all Members within 10 calendar days of the meeting;
- The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending, no Member has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes.

Note take responsible: each WPL is responsible for taking notes and sending them to the PC. A shared document to work on the minutes will be distributed among participants and is responsibility of each WPL to complete their slot.

WP meetings

WPL are responsible for the implementation of the tasks and preparation of deliverables. They will set (*if necessary*) the number and periodicity of meetings with partners needed to progress on the tasks, corresponding deliverables and to achieve milestones and the objectives established in the DoA.

⁸ For the shake of efficient resource management, the General Assembly meetings will coincide with the Transnational Project Meetings.

Task-specific meetings can be scheduled freely by agreement of partners involved in the task. The organisation and chairing of such meetings are the responsibility of the WP or task leader, in case of a task-specific meeting. The superseding WPL can also call for task-specific meetings.

3.4. External communication

Communication of the project and the Consortium with society and key external stakeholders is defined in several deliverables and planning documents of the project. WP4 & WP7 deals with Dissemination and Communication objectives and the development of the suitable strategies and tools.

3.4.1. Dissemination strategy

The Dissemination and social marketing strategy will be developed in Task 4.1. & Task 7.1. (reported on *D.4.1|M6* & *D.7.1|M22*) and will deal with messages, target audiences, channels, social media, marketing approaches, communication and dissemination activities in order to reach maximum impact of the project. Partners will be given guidelines in order to support these activities and thus maximise impact and generation of awareness. This document will also include guidelines for scientific publications.

3.4.2. Visual identity

In the framework of Task 4.2 and D4.1 (due in M3), the visual identity for CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB (logos, branding, graphic elements) will be designed. Visual identity and graphical guidelines have to be followed by all partners in each document and output resulting from the project. Templates for publications, presentations, deliverables, project documentation such as agenda, minutes, work presentations will also be provided by WP4&WP7.

Important to take into account as stated in ARTICLE 17 of the Grant Agreement, all recipients of EU funding have a general obligation to acknowledge the origin and ensure the visibility of any EU funding received. More information on this regard can be found on the following links:

- [Communicating and raising EU visibility - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eu-visibility/)

- Communication and Visibility Rules European Union funding programmes for 2021–2027. Guidelines: [communication and visibility rules-NA0121482ENN.pdf](#)

4. Document management

This section elaborates on key considerations related to the tools, creation, management, and official delivery of project documentation. It encompasses topics such as shared repository management, outlining the procedure for delivering deliverables, and handling other documents such as presentations and meeting minutes.

4.1. Online Project repository folder

The software tool to be used as repository for all the documentation generated within the project is SharePoint, GDPR compliant. The PC has provided the whole consortium access to this repository. The access will include the permissions for partners at least to create folders, download, upload, edit documents and to work online in a collaborative way.

As it can be seen in Image 3, the SharePoint site is composed of several tools⁹ namely “Calendar”¹⁰, “Project Deliverables & Milestones” & “Documents”.

Image 3 CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB SharePoint

⁹ CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB SharePoint is a live page, what implies that during the project lifecycle it might experiment some changes which will be communicated to the consortium in dully time. This disclaimer applies to every sub-page of the shared folder.

¹⁰ Already explained in 3.3 Internal communication.

4.1.1. Project Deliverables & Milestones

In this site all the deliverables (both internal and final) are included, as well as the deadlines and responsible. Each deliverable leader must update the status of their deliverable in this site. Moreover, it also serves as consulting page.

external_SharePoint

HE_K_CCRI_101135174 #

Grupo privado ☆ No se sigue 👤 53 miembros

Inicio + Nuevo Editar en vista de cuadrícula Compartir Exportar Automatizar Integrar Finalizar instalación Todos los elementos

Conversaciones

Bloc de notas

Compartido con nosotros

Calendar

Project deliverables & Mil...

Continuous Reporting

Documents

Papelera de reciclaje

Editar

Volver a la versión clásica de SharePoint

Progress tracker list ☆

Work item	Description	Category	Progress	Start date	Due date	Assigned to	Notes
D1.2 Network Coordination Guidelines-1 (L...	D1.2 will consist on a document containing the coordination mechanisms and tools to be used during the project with regard the CCRI, CCRI-CSO, partnering organizations and stakeholders. The reference task is T1.3 D1.2 will be delivered in M15 but a first version will be delivered	R — Document, r...	Not started	January 01	March 31	Alba Matamoros	LEADER: 1. KVC DISS LEVEL: PU
D1.2 Network Coordination Guidelines-1	D1.2 will consist on a document containing the coordination mechanisms and tools to be used during the project with regard the CCRI, CCRI-CSO, partnering organizations and stakeholders. The reference task is T1.3	R — Document, r...	Not started	January 01	March 31, 2025		LEADER: 1. KVC DISS LEVEL: PU
D1.3 Ethics and Data Management Plan-1	This Deliverable will consist on a document outlining the data to be collected and how they will be collected, processed, shared, stored, accessed and protected. It will include information on data management during and after the project. It will also contain a section on Ethics and ethics management	DMP — Data Ma...	Not started	January 01	June 30, 2025		LEADER: 1. KVC DISS LEVEL: PU
D1.4 Clustering activities-1	D1.4 will contain a description of the clustering activities with other EU projects selected under the CircBio 01-1 during the first 18 months of the project. The reference task is T1.6	R — Document, r...	Not started	January 01	June 30, 2025		LEADER: 1. KVC DISS LEVEL: PU
D2.1 CE projects/initiatives, GPs & less succ...	D2.1 will contain all initiatives, projects, GPs and less successful cases identified and analysed during the project following ad hoc formats. K-CCRI will analyse at least 150 CE projects and showcase at least 40 CE Good Practices and 20 'less successful' ones. The reference tasks are T2.1 and T2.3	R — Document, r...	Not started	January 01	May 31, 2025		LEADER: 2. CETEC DISS LEVEL: PU
D2.2 Resources compilation to support a su...	D2.2 will gather all useful and supporting Circular Economy materials, tools and resources (including the identification of relevant synergistic local policy plans) that will feed the K-CCRI platform. The reference tasks are T2.2 and T2.4	OTHER	Not started	January 01	May 31, 2025		LEADER: 2. CETEC DISS LEVEL: PU

Image 4 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB : Project deliverables & milestones | SharePoint

4.1.2. Documents

The structure of the repository folder is as follows:

00_Templates

01_LogosI

02_Document_templates

03_Logos_CE_CCRI_&_visual_guide

In this folder all the information regarding templates (minutes, presentations, deliverable status report, change log...), partners logos, official EC logos is saved.

01_Administrative&Financial

00_EC_Reference_documents

01_Grant_Agreement

02_Consortium_Agreement

03_Amedments

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04_Reporting_M12

Within the administrative and financial documentation section, it can be found essential materials for managing project affairs. This includes reference documents provided by the EC for guidance, the official grant agreement outlining funding terms, the CA detailing partner responsibilities, and any amendments made to these agreements for reference and compliance purposes.

02_Meetings

01_WP_Meetings (*i.e. WP1 specific meetings with L1, WP2 specific meetings about the platform...*)

02_Project_Management_Board_Meetings

03_General Assembly & Project_Meetings (*i.e. face to face consortium meetings*)

01_Meeting_Place_Organiser: Agenda, Presentations, Logistics&Attendance, Minutes, Photos

04_Technical_Committee_Meetings

05_Review_Meetings_PO

06_Project meetings (*i.e. monthly consortium meetings information*)

00_Online_Consortium_meeting_date

Folder MEETINGS will include all the necessary information about project meetings. Each meeting folder will contain documentation used and resulting from the meetings, such as agenda, minutes, attendee registration, presentations and access to the sessions recorded (*if needed*). **Same naming must be used among different folders.**

03_WorkPackages

There is one folder for each WP, with its corresponding number. Inside each WP folder, a subfolder for each Task with numeration has been created. Each task folder follows the same structure:

00_Obsol

01_Deliverable: folder to work collaboratively on a deliverable and where the revision procedure must take place.

02_Workshop_events: folder to save all the information regarding workshops or events (external or internal) related with the task.

03_Literature: relevant literature for the consortium, worth to share, and relevant to the task.

04_TechnicalWork: folder to work and save information relevant for the task but that are not the final output (surveys, templates for collecting information...).

📁 04_SubmittedDeliverables

Final approved deliverables downloaded from the Funding & Tenders' portal will be saved in this folder (EU Approved).

📁 General: automatically linked folder within the Teams channel designated solely for storage purposes. No data should be saved or deleted within this folder.

📁 Email attachments: automatically linked folder within Outlook designated solely for storage purposes. No data should be saved or deleted within this folder.

📄 KCCRI_Contact_data

4.2. Deliverables

Deliverable submission is an obligation according to the article 7 of the Grant Agreement. The PC is responsible for submitting all deliverables at their due date according to the List of Deliverables shown in Annex I Part A of the Grant Agreement (Pages 15-23, see table 7).

Table 13 - CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB deliverables list

D.No	Deliverable name	WP No.	Leader	Type	Diss. level	Deliv.Date
D1.1	<i>Project Management Handbook-1</i>	1	KVC	R	PU	M15 (March 2025)
D1.2	<i>Network Coordination Guidelines-1</i>	1	KVC	R	PU	M15 (March 2025)
D1.3	<i>Ethics and Data Management Plan-1</i>	1	KVC	DMP	PU	M18 (June 2025)
D1.4	<i>Clustering activities-1</i>	1	KVC	R	PU	M18 (June 2025)
D2.1	<i>CE projects/initiatives, GPs & less successful cases</i>	2	CETEC	R	PU	M17 (May 2025)
D2.2	<i>Resources compilation to support a successful transition to a circular economy in cities/regions (Folder with materials, tools and resources)</i>	2	CETEC	OTHER	PU	M17 (May 2025)

D3.1	<i>CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Support Pathways</i>	3	UVEG	R	PU	M17 (May 2025)
D3.2	<i>On-line repository of resources, including the database /catalogue of sectoral/cross-sectoral technologies that facilitate circularity</i>	3	CETEC	DATA	PU	M17 (May 2025)
D3.3	<i>Delivery of first services (1st 18 months of the project)</i>	3	UVEG	R	PU	M17 (May 2025)
D3.4	<i>Mentoring Guide</i>	3	KVC	R	PU	M9 (September 2024)
D4.1	<i>Dissemination and Communication Strategy</i>	4	ICONS	R	PU	M6 (June 2024)
D4.2	<i>D&C activities and impact analysis-1</i>	4	ICONS	R	PU	M16 (April 2025)
D4.3	<i>Community building.</i>	4	ALDA	R	PU	M16 (April 2025)
D5.1	<i>Network Coordination Guidelines - 2</i>	5	KVC	R	PU	M33 (September 2026)
D5.2	<i>Project Management Handbook-2</i>	5	KVC	R	PU	M33 (September 2026)
D5.3	<i>Ethics and Data Management Plan-2</i>	5	KVC	DMP	PU	M36 (December 2026)
D5.4	<i>Clustering activities-2</i>	5	KVC	R	PU	M36 (December 2026)
D6.1	<i>Delivery of services (2nd 18 months of the project)</i>	6	UVEG	R	PU	M35 (November 2026)
D7.1	<i>Dissemination and Communication Strategy-2 (Update)</i>	7	ICONS	R	PU	M22 (October 2025)
D7.2	<i>D&C activities and impact analysis-2</i>	7	ICONS	R	PU	M35 (November 2026)
D7.3	<i>Community building-2</i>	7	ALDA	R	PU	M35 (November 2026)
D8.1	<i>Exploitation and sustainability strategy</i>	8	KVC	R	PU	M36 (December 2026)

D8.2	<i>Policy recommendations and lessons learnt</i>	8	ALDA	R	PU	M35 (November 2026)
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The deliverables will be prepared according to the Deliverable Template (*to be included as Annex to this document when ready*), in compliance with its format, logos, statements and disclaimers.

In the phase of Deliverable elaboration, the following rules have to be taken into consideration:

- The executive summary will be a section no more than one page that summarizes the important points of the deliverable in a very clear and exhaustive way.
- The Introduction section should outline clearly the Purpose and Scope of the deliverable with clear objectives from the beginning.
- A Conclusions section should be included.
- The document has to be concise: giving a lot of information clearly and in a few words; expressing what needs to be said without unnecessary words; avoiding useless lengthening.
- Pay attention to glaring typos, leaving the spell check active (*always in UK English*) and reading once more the document before considering it as consolidated and ready to be checked by the reviewers.
- To avoid repeating contents already described in previous Deliverables or in the Grant Agreement (always use references for that).
- Any bibliographic citation has to be referenced, using APAP as citation method.
- The first draft of the deliverable must be ready a month before its due date, for its peer review, and the final version must be sent to the PC a week before its due date.
- The PC will store the final versions of the deliverables in the corresponding folder on the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB platform and put them at the disposal of all members of the consortium for consultation.

Although there are no requirements on the minimum or maximum number of pages, each Deliverable should provide sufficient information to both the REA and external reviewers to assess the project progress and its results. Also, consider that the Deliverables will be public, so easy to understand and follow for interested stakeholders. Therefore, Deliverables have to be very concise about which content to include in the documents. The right size for a given

Deliverable depends largely on the topic, the objective, etc., but as a general rule, it is considered reasonable that Deliverables should not exceed 30 pages. Annexes may be added.

4.2.1. Templates

Templates based on project visual identity and logo will be provided by WP4. These templates and logos must be used by Consortium in all the documents generated within the project: Deliverables, presentations, minutes, agenda and rest of documentation.

4.2.2. Deliverable Status Information

The following states are used for deliverables:

- Draft: The working versions of a deliverable, i.e. work in progress which is not ready for review yet.
- For EU Approval (implying consortium approved): A deliverable which has been accepted by the project internal reviewers and is therefore sent to the EC (for approval).
- EU Approved: A deliverable accepted by the EC and therefore ready for publication.

4.2.3. Naming Conventions and Versioning

Both the draft and final versions will be numbered according to the Deliverable number shown into the List of Deliverables shown in Annex I Part A of the Grant Agreement (Pages 15-23), adding the version code that will be V0.x for consecutive draft versions and V1.x for consecutive versions of the final edition:

Code for draft versions → Dx.y_V0.z

Code for final edition versions → Dx.y_V1.z

4.2.4. Tracking of Changes and Commenting

In the process of producing a Deliverable, changes, suggestions and other contributions to the document will be done using the options for tracking of changes and introduction of comments. Contributors must make sure that the author of the comments and changes is properly identified.

4.2.5. Roles and responsibilities

Deliverable lead beneficiary: Lead beneficiaries are the main editors and lead the Deliverable production process, being the main responsible for the submission of the document in due time. They are also the main contact point with the other roles, being in charge of asking contributions to other involved partners, uploading the document to the right location in the project platform and notify the PC that it is ready for starting the Quality Check. It is in charge of providing an update of the Deliverables progress and explanation on eventual expected delay to the PC.

Once the peer review related comments are received (if any), the lead beneficiary has to ensure that such comments/requests have been indeed addressed (involving, if it is the case, also the contributors).

Deliverable contributor: participants in the production of the Deliverable by contributing with content and supporting the lead beneficiary in producing a high-quality document, addressing eventual reviewer comments and requests.

PC: the PC must submit to the EC the deliverables identified in Annex 1 of the GA, in accordance with the timing and conditions set out in it.

Deliverable reviewer: partner responsible for meticulously evaluating submitted documents against the criteria established in section 5 to ensure accuracy, alignment with project objectives, and adherence to guidelines.

4.2.6. EU Response to deliverables

Once a deliverable has been officially submitted, EU response may be one of the following 4 status: NOT SUBMITTED, REQUEST FOR REVISION, ACCEPTED, REJECTED. If the Deliverable is rejected, the project officer contacts with the PC to prepare and submit a new version. If the deliverable is accepted, it will be published following the CCRI procedures.

5. Quality management

Section 5 from encapsulates the **Quality Management (QM)** protocol for the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB project, integrating both the foundational principles of QA (**Quality Assurance**) and the practical mechanisms and checkpoints of QC (**Quality Control**). Furthermore, it introduces pivotal dimensions for both QA and QC, aiming to evaluate the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB project comprehensively and all the scientific and technical outputs generated throughout its duration.

The **primary objective** of QM is to assess all technical and scientific facets that are, or might be, integral to a quality-focused evaluation. This evaluation also incorporates the core values of the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB project: ensuring the effectiveness of all outputs and defining quality based on established standards. This implies that quality is gauged in conjunction with any other component that can be evaluated or compared against similar benchmarks (standards). The quality standards used within the present project management handbook are based on the **United Nations Evaluation Group Standards for Evaluation in the UN System**¹¹.

It's crucial to note that the Quality evaluation does not encompass the assessment of the project's overall impact or its outcomes. Instead, it aims to measure the continuum of accomplishment and excellence of all outputs stemming from CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB.

Key Concepts.

Differences between **QC** and **QA** within a general **QM** framework should be established: firstly, QC could be considered as a part of the more general QA protocol, which is framed on a QM approach. The **QA** relates to the processes in which deliverables are created and, so, the elaboration, the revision and also the principles for assessing the quality that is being followed during the preparation and delivery of these type of outputs. The **QC** refers to the procedures to be conducted for defining and ensuring the “acceptable quality”, and also the completeness and correctness of these outputs. QA starts before the execution of all key activities

¹¹ UNEG Standards for Evaluation are available at <http://www.unevaluation.org/document/download/2787>

comprising the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB project, and QC is executed on demand as outputs are being developed and delivered.

Figure 3 - QM key concepts

To sum up, “QC is about adherence to requirements. QA is generic and does not concern the specific requirements of the product being developed”¹². Both are two inseparable parts of the QM, which also foresees issues and raises corrective actions in-line with the protocols agreed by the whole consortium.

In the case of CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB , key outputs to be considered within the QA and QC are:

- Deliverables
- Scientific publications
- Transnational Project Meetings

While scientific publications could be considered as dissemination and communication materials, the characteristics and features of the research outputs require, in the case of CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB , a separate consideration for evaluating them from both points of view.

¹² Quality assurance and Quality control, at https://www.diffen.com/difference/Quality_Assurance_vs_Quality_Control

Consequently, the QC for the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB project will measure and evaluate key dimensions for **deliverables, scientific publications and dissemination and communication materials**, considering the baseline requirements and general revision procedures established in the QA, which will be separated into four plans: technical quality, scientific quality, transnational project meetings quality and internal project quality (described in sections below).

5.1. Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) in CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB

5.1.1. QA: methods, means and phases

The evaluation will be conducted using an Internal Evaluation Approach. Internal evaluation refers to the assessment process undertaken by the institution or individuals directly responsible for the activities being evaluated. Specifically, the evaluation will involve:

- **UVEG:** Task 1.4 -Internal evaluation, QC & risk management- leader. While all partners should participate in QM, the coordination and primary responsibility rests with UVEG.
- **KVC:** Leader of the WP1 & WP5 in which this deliverable is framed and PC.
- **CETEC:** Technical coordinator of CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB will also be an active part of the evaluation process checking the quality of the technical deliverables and tasks.
- **The GA:** Its primary role concerning QA is to suggest and support corrective actions stemming from the QC process and feedback collected by the evaluation group. All partners will be part of the internal peer review process and responsible to implement their corresponding activities with the expected quality.
- **The PMB:** Their primary role concerning QA is to support the evaluation group in assessing technical and technological quality.
- **The Advisory Board (AB):** there is not foreseen the participation of external and independent experts to provide external validation, facilitate knowledge exchange, and

assist in disseminating results. In CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB , the CCRI and CCRI-CSO will review some of the actions, deliverables and process before its publication so they will act as a kind of project AB to ensure the alignment of CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB with the CCRI initiative.

Internal evaluators are distinct from the external evaluation performed by the AB members. Internal evaluators are directly supervised by the PC, CETEC and UVEG. They have a continuous responsibility for evaluation, as detailed in this report. The evaluation results will guide the QM decision-making process through recommendations, serving both to provide information and influence behaviour. Subsequent updates to this document will incorporate these recommendations within the "Feedback and corrective actions" section.

QA will be implemented in two phases:

PHASE 1- Conduct quality planning (M1-3)

Planning for quality is a key element of the development of the action plan and is the responsibility of the PC. The QA framework is included in this Project Management Handbook (D.1.1.) and aims at ensuring the compliance of quality standards, which guarantee that:

- a) a certain output allows a clear and complete understanding of its results, and
- b) produced credible knowledge deemed to be a sound basis for decision making.

PHASE 2- Implement QA framework (M4-36)

The QA framework outlines how project quality will be managed, incorporating methodologies, standards, guidelines, and organisational structures. It relies on established methods and evolves through updates and modifications to adapt to project progress and address issues. It encompasses technical, scientific, procedural, and internal quality aspects comprehensively.

5.1.2. QC Procedure and reporting

The QC plans the execution of the principles and necessities explained in the QA through various procedures and tools to be detailed along this section. QC activities will be reported in two moments. Firstly, in the D.1.1 Project Management Handbook to be delivered in **Month 15**, and finally in **Month 33** in the deliverable D.5.2. Project Management Handbook-2.

As mentioned before, **the key element of the QC is the revision of project deliverables**: the objective is to verify if they comply with specifications and standards and meet the requirements set. This will be a continuous process, where the deliverables from the tasks are examined in detail with particular emphasis on quality control checkpoints – pre-defined in this document. The evaluation of deliverables will entail the technical quality. **QC also includes the review of scientific outputs, transnational project meetings and the project's internal progress.**

Technical Quality – Deliverables

The technical QA applies to deliverables and, also, to the project as a whole (its management and workflow). The evaluation of the quality will assess the **project outputs (Deliverables)** against specific quality criteria (QC) in order to ensure that the proper quality standards are met (QA). The project deliverables will be evaluated against the UNEG standards and will be assessed as highly satisfactory when they are credible reports that address the evaluation purpose and objectives based on evidence, and therefore can be used with confidence.

For CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB , the Quality-related qualitative indicators are:

1. Relevance to objectives - the deliverable matches the objectives listed in the Grant Agreement.
2. Well structured, logical and clear report.
3. Clear and full description of the 'object' of the analysis.
4. The analysis' purpose, objectives and scope are fully explained.
5. Appropriate and sound methodology.
6. Findings, conclusions, recommendations and lessons learned are based on evidence and sound analysis.

The present QA will also determine whether the project allowed a clear and complete understanding and produced credible knowledge deemed to be a sound basis for decision making. These indicators are well reflected in the Annex 8.5. (Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire), which includes the tool for controlling the quality for deliverables.

QC Process

The evaluation will be performed through an **internal peer review process** prior to the release of the project deliverables (ex-ante evaluation). In order to perform the evaluation, a

questionnaire for the quality control (Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire, annex 8.4) has been designed. The partners on a rotating basis, and based on their expertise, will review and approve before submitting the deliverables against the quality criteria and fill the referring Quality Evaluation Questionnaire and send back comments to the deliverables' author(s) who will take them into account in the final version of the deliverable. Then, the evaluation team (UVEG, CETEC and KVC) will make a final check before the deliverable submission and dissemination.

The internal peer-review follows the principles and execution of the procedures identified in QA: two project partners will conduct a quality control evaluation:

1. **Preliminary control by the WPL (-3 weeks):** deliverable received by the 5th of the delivery month.
2. **Internal Peer-review (-3 weeks).** Comments and corrective actions delivered by the 15th of the delivery month. Deliverable responsible partner then implements corrections by the 24th of the delivery month.
3. **QC and approval by the PC.** Deliverable received by the 24th of the delivery month from the deliverable responsible partner. Comments and corrective actions delivered by the 30th of the delivery month.
4. Implementation of corrective actions by deliverable responsible partners and **submission to project's SharePoint.**
5. Submission of the deliverable by the PC.

To sum up, deliverables are revised by two partners selected accordingly to their expertise and workload, following these three selection criteria for reviewers:

- Background and expertise.
- Not involved directly in the deliverable elaboration and related tasks.
- Not involved in the release of deliverables for the same deadline (avoiding overburden).

The document containing the preliminary distribution of review responsibilities among the project partners is located in the **project's SharePoint as an online spreadsheet**. This distribution is flexible and may be altered as workload or other reasons warrant.

Sometimes, an **external review** can be also by CCRI or CCRI-CSO. In this case the process and the timeline is the same but adding the CCRI and CCRI-CSO in the process.

Scientific Quality – Scientific Outputs

While this project does not primarily involve conducting research, there exist certain activities within the project that may incidentally lead to research outcomes. To cite a few examples:

- Task 3.1 entails evaluating and analysing the circular economy development process within a specific region from a systemic perspective, and formulating supportive developmental pathways, which could be of scientific interest.
- Task 3.4 involves the assessment of workshop outcomes and the application of methodologies relevant to the academic domain of democracy, such as deliberative dialogues.
- Within WP 8, the focus is on developing policy recommendations among other activities, which might be of academic interest in the circular economy field.

It is therefore prudent to establish a framework not for the purpose of scientific validation, but rather to facilitate the reporting of any scientific outputs that may emerge from the project. It should be noted, however, that **not all scientific outputs will be subject to review**. Specifically, the project will not cover evaluations of conference presentations, posters, and similar outputs.

The primary focus will be on reviewing **scientific articles and position papers**. These documents are considered crucial for maintaining the project's commitment to QM and ensuring the relevance and accuracy of the scientific contributions made.

Scientific Quality will be revised by partners, selected accordingly to the procedures specified in the previous section. The corresponding questionnaires and instruments (See 8 Annexes) will be aimed at facilitating the QC of articles, papers and conference proceedings before their submission.

Scientific quality will be measured through three dimensions: scientific adequacy, rigour and potential scale-up of results.

Scientific adequacy. It is measured against the:

- Credibility of findings.
- Scientific and methodological rigor for validating the hypothesis or answering the research questions.
- Trustworthiness of the results in light to the acceptance (by the scientific

community) of the methods used.

- Consistency with the project objectives.
- Alignment with the project scope.

Rigour. It is measured against the:

- Reliability of the methods used for reaching the results.
- Scientific validity of results.
- Consistency of the results and its discussion.
- Reliability of the conclusions raised from the analysis and the discussion of findings.
- Transferability of the research results.
- Confirmability of the research results.

Potential to scale-up the results. While scaling-up is not an internal measurement of reliability of the research, given the scope and aims of CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB , it is included. The QA-specific **activities**, considered separately from the QC procedures, tasks and checkpoints, are not scheduled in advance. As the project progresses and mitigation and enhancement measures emerge from the feedback, the QC checkpoints, and the internal discussions within the consortium, the principles which rule the QA approach explained above may change. Thus, as it has been previously explained, the present deliverable is a dynamic and practice-oriented document. It is susceptible to be updated on demand and depending on the necessities of the project.

QC Process

The article or position paper will be uploaded to the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB repository, if possible **3 weeks in advance**, for sharing with the entire consortium. The corresponding or main author will notify the project manager (KVC; PC) and the Dissemination Leader (ICONS) of the upload. KVC and/or ICONS will inform the partners of the update and will determine who should review the scientific output. The criteria for this decision, similar to that for deliverables, include:

- workload
- expertise
- non-involvement in the creation of the scientific production.

However, given the nature of scientific dissemination and the unpredictability of call for papers and tight deadlines for congresses and events, it might not always be possible to notify about the output within the ideal timeframes and following the correct procedure. In such cases, the revision will be directly overseen by the PC and the Dissemination Leader.

Organizational Quality – Transnational Project Meetings

To ensure the effectiveness and efficiency of these meetings, UVEG will distribute the Transnational Project Meetings (TPM) Quality Evaluation Questionnaire (see 8 Annexes) following the conclusion of each TPM.

This questionnaire employs a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) to evaluate several facets of the meetings, such as their relevance and objectives, the preparation and organisation, participant engagement, communication and clarity, outcomes achieved, and the overall added value.

By gathering and analysing feedback from this questionnaire, we aim to pinpoint both the strengths and areas requiring enhancement in the execution of TPM. This systematic approach enables continuous improvement in our organisational practices and will contribute to the overall success of the project.

QC Process

The Internal evaluation, QC & risk management- leader (UVEG) will distribute the TPM Quality Evaluation Questionnaire to all partners following the conclusion of each TPM. All attendees are required to complete the questionnaire within a two-week period.

Internal Quality – Process evaluation

The internal evaluation framework forms a crucial component of our quality management strategy. This framework encompasses two principal dimensions:

- **Effectiveness Assessment:** Our first priority is to ensure the attainment of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as outlined in the Grant Agreement.
- **Transversal-Process Evaluation:** The second dimension extends beyond mere KPI achievement to evaluate the broader aspects of the project. This holistic assessment aims to capture the consortium's perspective on various facets, including:
 - The overall functionality and coherence of the project.
 - The efficiency and effectiveness of project management and coordination.

- The reach and impact of dissemination activities.
- Satisfaction with the outcomes derived from the identification, analysis, and customization of materials.
- The perceived impact and success of our workshops and other engagement activities.
- Contentment with the functionality and user experience of the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB platform.

To facilitate this comprehensive evaluation, we will employ the Internal Evaluation Survey (see 8 Annexes), an online tool designed to gauge the cross-sectional dimensions of the project's operation. This survey aims not only to assess the tangible outputs but also to provide insights into the project's process quality and overall progress. By integrating feedback from this survey, we aim to identify areas for improvement and reinforce our project's strengths, ensuring a cohesive, effective, and impactful project execution.

QC Process

- **Effectiveness Assessment:** KPIs verification process will be executed through the Deliverables Status Report. UVEG will conduct a thorough review of the KPIs, determining their applicability to specific tasks, and subsequently integrating them into the respective deliverable status report templates. This structured approach facilitates the continuous monitoring and evaluation of CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB 's project's effectiveness. Within the Internal Quarterly reports, a specific subsection will be integrated for partners to report on the progress and achievement of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for which they are directly responsible.
- **Internal-Process Evaluation:** Internal Evaluation Survey will be administered at two critical junctures: firstly, in conjunction with the preparation of D.1.1 Project Management Handbook (due M15), prior to the project's mid-term. This will provide a comprehensive overview of the partners' perceptions regarding the project's progress at this halfway point, enabling the identification and implementation of any necessary corrective measures. Secondly, it will be distributed during the final months of the project to capture the partners' overall assessment and reflections on the project in its entirety, as per preparation of D.5.2 Project Management Handbook-2 (due M33). The Internal Evaluation Survey will contain permanent items (see 8 Annexes) and variable

items covering the different WPs which will be included at a later stage and adapted at the time the questionnaire is administered to better reflect the partners' assessment of the outputs achieved up to that point.

6. Risk management

The **Risk Management and Contingency Plan (RMCP)** is an integral component of WP1 & WP5 in the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB project. While risk management is a collective responsibility across all WPs, each WPL will collaborate with their respective teams to identify risks specific to their activities.

Risk management in CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB is a collaborative task, spearheaded by the PC and executed in tandem with all partners.

The overarching aim of risk management is to pre-emptively identify, manage, and mitigate any potential challenges that might jeopardize the project's completion or the realisation of its objectives, as outlined in the Grant Agreement.

Definitions

- **Risk:** A potential scenario that could adversely affect the project's objectives or planned activities.
- **Risk Management:** A proactive approach to ensuring project success. It involves early detection of potential challenges and devising mitigation and contingency plans to either prevent or minimize the likelihood and impact of these challenges.
- **Contingency Measure:** A planned action designed to counteract the negative effects of a risk, potentially even eliminating the risk.

As the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB project progresses, consortium members gain a clearer understanding of potential challenges, necessitating periodic updates to the project's risk identification.

Categories of Risks and Contingency Measures

For CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB, risks will be categorised by WPs related risks, and will contemplate:

- **Administrative Risks:** Pertaining to consortium structure, partner conflicts, and communication with stakeholders and the European Commission (EC).
- **Financial Risks:** Concerning the financial management aspects of the project.
- **Technical and Operational Risks:** Related to the planning, development, and execution of technical activities, including IT tool development, guideline creation,

dissemination, communication, and exploitation tasks.

- **Research-Related Risks:** Associated with research tasks, including challenges in pilot phases, such as sample selection biases or recruitment issues.

6.1. RMCP Procedures

1 - Registry of Risks and Contingency Measures

A dedicated online registry has been established to document all project-related risks. This registry, accessible as an online spreadsheet in the project's SharePoint, will capture:

1. Partner acronym for clarity.
2. Risk detection date.
3. Type of risk.
4. Affected WP.
5. Detailed risk description.
6. Contingency measure.
7. Potential project-wide impact (Likert scale, 1-5).
8. Likelihood of occurrence (Likert scale, 1-5).
9. Proposed mitigation measures.
10. Estimated mitigation measure efficiency (Likert scale, 1-5).

Each risk will have designated measures, responsibilities, and action plans. As part of the 6-month internal reporting, the PC will conduct a risk assessment, updating the Risk Registry based on the findings.

2 - Update of the RMCP

This document is designed to be both user-friendly and adaptable. UVEG will ensure its regular update, aligning it with the evolving needs and challenges of the CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB project lifecycle. The RMCP will be subject to regular updates to ensure its relevance and efficacy throughout the project lifecycle recording all the risks and mitigations put in place in the online risk registry. This updating process will be systematically integrated into our operational procedures in the following manner:

- WP Meetings Integration: During these meetings, a dedicated agenda item will be allocated for risk review. This will involve a detailed discussion of existing risks outlined in the RMCP

and the identification of any new risks that have emerged since the last update. This practice ensures continuous monitoring and responsiveness to the evolving risk landscape.

- Deliverable Status Reports: Lead partners for each deliverable will contribute to this dynamic risk management approach by updating the risk section within their Deliverable Status Reports. This includes evaluating ongoing risks as well as identifying and documenting any new risks since the last RMCP update. By doing so, each deliverable's specific risk context is kept current and actionable.
- Continuous RMCP Updates: The RMCP (online registry) will be updated by UVEG following each Work Package meeting and after the submission of WP internally quarterly reports that introduce new risks or changes to existing risks. This cyclical process ensures that the RMCP remains a living document, reflective of the project's current risk profile.

7. Monitoring project performance

7.1. Periodic Reports

CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB counts with 2 different Periodic Reports (PR) along its life:

- PR1 (M1-M18)
- PR2 (M19-M36)

Periodic reports are official reports to be submitted to EC in terms stated in Grant Agreement. These periodic report entails, afterwards, a review by an external reviewer and are organised systematically after each reporting period. The project review is an in-depth examination of the project technical and financial implementation by the consortium. In the chart below the main reporting tasks are shown:

Image 5 - Reporting procedure

Any change request affecting the PR submission (i.e. date of delivery, number of reports, etc) should be done through an amendment process.

7.2. Internal Project Monitoring

The purpose of monitoring the project performance is to collect information to evaluate the state of the project’s progress and overall health. In order to allow the regular tracking of

project progress and to make sure that possible problems are recognised early so that there is time to take corrective actions, a system of interim reports and responsibilities has been designed.

The PC will use as baseline the information included in the DoA as a reference for monitoring the project performance and will track the scope and schedule using the information gathered from the meeting minutes and WP leaders reporting.

The PC will request the following inputs from the WP leaders in order to collect all the information necessary for the project progress monitoring and control:

- WP three term plans [M9-M18-M27] [WPX_WPPlan_M1-M18]
- WP internally quarterly reports [Quarterly] [IQR_WPX_MX-MX]

7.2.1. Planning: WP three term plans

The DoA includes the project Gantt and scheduled milestones, with a detailed description of the objectives and work to be done in every WP and sub-tasks. To assure the proper performance of all project activities, **every WP leader** must prepare, together with the task leaders, a WP work plan in a Gantt chart reflecting the work for the following three terms [M9-M18-M27], trying to itemize all activities required as much as possible to ease the monitoring of the WP progress by the task leaders, WP leader and PC. The WP three terms plans will be delivered to the PC.

The templates to be completed will be stored into each WP folder in the shared repository.

7.2.2. Reporting: WP internally reports

These reports are required by the PC to monitor the progress of the project. Each partner will contribute, sending details on the progress in their own activities to the respective WP leader. Annex 8.3. presents the template each WP leader is required to use and instructions on how to complete it. The template includes, besides all the activities carried out, any deviation or change of what was planned, issues that may come up, results and achievements and the risks identification and analysis. WP leaders will produce 6 reports during each reporting period (M1-M18). Each quarter, the WPL will complete the corresponding report, which will be discussed in the monthly meeting that corresponds to each quarter [M3, M6, M9, M12, M15, M18, M21, M24, M27, M30, M33].

The templates to be completed will be stored into each WP folder in the shared repository.

7.3. Administrative and financial coordination.

The Administrative and Financial justifications in the lump sum scheme rely on the technical one. Beneficiaries must submit adequate records and supporting documents demonstrating the proper implementation of the action as described in Annex 1 (i.e. technical documents, publications, deliverables and explanations supporting the scientific and technical implementation of the action). The administrative justification is not required; therefore, the PC will not request any type of document as needed. That is, supporting documentation for costs actually incurred are not required because there will be no financial reviews, checks or cost audits. **However, each partner is responsible for providing supporting documents in accordance with their national laws.**

Additionally, timesheets or other documents demonstrating time devotion remain mandatory. All the legal requirements to be taken into consideration are included in the Project CA & Grant Agreement. Partners must read thoroughly the Grant Agreement and its annexes.

7.3.1. Internal Justification M12

Together with technical report in M12, partners will include the percentage of resources invested in each WP. It should be in line with the technical development of each WP.

7.3.2. First Report Justification M18

Together with technical First Period Report M18, partners will include the percentage of resources invested in each WP. It should be in line with the technical development of each WP.

7.3.3. Final Report Justification M36

Together with technical Final Report M36, partners will include the percentage of resources invested in each WP. It should be in line with the technical development of each WP.

7.3.4. Useful resources

The EC facilitate guidelines, samples and special rules to justify properly the Horizon Europe projects.

- Horizon Europe Reference Documents: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents;programCode=H2020?selectedProgrammePeriod=2021-2027&selectedProgramme=HORIZON>
- How to manage your Lump Sum project. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/how-to-manage-your-lump-sum-grants_en.pdf

8. Annexes

8.1. Distribution of deliverable reviewers

Table 14 - Distribution of deliverable reviewers

Deliverable name	Lead Beneficiary	Due date	Deliverable Reviewer 1	Deliverable Reviewer 2	Date when the Quality Control process begins
D.1.1 Project Management Handbook-1	KVC	M15	CETEC	KFL	5th March 2025
D.1.2 Network Coordination Guidelines-1	KVC	M15	EURADA	ICONS	5th March 2025
D.1.3 Ethics and Data Management Plan-1	KVC	M18	UVEG	FILSE	5th June 2025
D.1.4 Clustering activities-1	KVC	M18	EBN	EURADA	5th June 2025
D.2.1 CE projects/initiatives, GPs & less successful cases	CETEC	M17	FILSE	KVC	5th May 2025
D.2.2 Resources compilation to support a successful transition to a circular economy in cities/regions (Folder with materials, tools and resources)	CETEC	M17	UVEG	KVC	5th May 2025
D.3.1 CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB Support Pathways	UVEG	M17	ALDA	KVC	5th May 2025

D.3.2 On-line repository of resources, including the database /catalogue of sectoral/ cross-sectoral technologies that facilitate circularity	CETEC	M17	VTT	KVC	5th May 2025
D.3.3 Delivery of first services (1st 18 months of the project)	UVEG	M17	ALDA	KVC	5th May 2025
D.3.4 Mentoring Guide	KVC	M9	CETEC	INV	5th September 2024
D.4.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy	ICONS	M6	KFL	KVC	5th June 2024
D.4.2 D&C activities and impact analysis-1	ICONS	M16	INV	KVC	5th April 2025
D.4.3 Community building.	ALDA	M16	VTT	KVC	5th April 2025
D.5.1 Network Coordination Guidelines -2	KVC	M33	EURADA	ICONS	5th September 2026
D.5.2 Project Management Handbook-2	KVC	M33	CETEC	KFL	5th September 2026
D.5.3 Ethics and Data Management Plan-2	KVC	M36	UVEG	FILSE	5th December 2026
D.5.4 Clustering activities-2	KVC	M36	EBN	EURADA	5th December 2026
D.6.1 Delivery of services (2nd 18 months of the project)	UVEG	M35	ALDA	KVC	5th November 2026
D.7.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy-2 (Update)	ICONS	M22	KFL	KVC	5th October 2025
D.7.2 D&C activities and impact analysis-2	ICONS	M35	INV	KVC	5th November 2026

D.7.3 Community building-2	ALDA	M35	VTT	KVC	5th November 2026
D.8.1 Exploitation and sustainability strategy	KVC	M36	ICONS	EBN	5th December 2026
D.8.2 Policy recommendations and lessons learnt	ALDA	M35	UVEG	KVC	5th November 2026

8.2. Change Log template

Table 15 - Change Log template

Change Identification and Description	
ID <i>The change identifier</i>	
Category <i>Categorises the change</i>	Select one element
Title <i>A short title for the requested change</i>	
Description <i>A more detailed description of the requested change and the impact of not implementing the change</i>	
Status: <i>The status of the change can be any of the following: Submitted: This is the initial status. Use this while the requested change is still being specified.</i> <i>Assessing: Use this status to initiate an assessment.</i> <i>Waiting for approval: Use this to initiate approval. Before applying this status, ensure that the investigation is complete, and the estimates shown are correct.</i> <i>Approved: This status is set once the change has been approved, as proposed, or modified</i> <i>Rejected: This status is set if the change was rejected.</i>	Select one element

<p><i>Postponed: This status is set if the change is postponed indefinitely.</i></p> <p><i>Merged: This status indicates that the change has been merged into some other change, so it is no longer being actively handled. Merging is common when there are many changes.</i></p> <p><i>Implemented: This status indicates that the work implementing this change has been incorporated into the Project Work Plan.</i></p>	
<p>Requested by</p> <p><i>The name of the person requesting the change</i></p>	
<p>Date Identified (or Submission Date)</p> <p><i>The initial submission date of the change request</i></p>	
Change Assessment and Action Description	
<p>Action Details (effort & responsible)</p> <p><i>Description of the recommended action, including steps, deliverables, timescale, resources and effort involved.</i></p>	
<p>Size</p> <p><i>The effort required to implement the change.</i></p>	Select one element
<p>Priority</p> <p><i>Numerical value denoting the agreed priority of the change</i></p>	Select one element
<p>Target Delivery Date</p> <p><i>The target date for the change to be delivered</i></p>	
Change Approval	
<p>Escalation</p> <p><i>Escalation to the Directing or Steering layer is needed? (Yes or No).</i></p>	
<p>Decision</p> <p><i>The decision taken</i></p>	
<p>Decided by</p> <p><i>Person or committee that denied or approved the change</i></p>	
<p>Decision Date</p> <p><i>Date on which the decision was made</i></p>	

8.3. WP internally quarterly report – template

Template example: WP2 Internally Quarterly Report

[Reporting process — Lump sum - IT How To - Funding Tenders Opportunities \(europa.eu\)](#)

INSTRUCTIONS:

This technical report should focus on the completion of work packages (in particular, when you declare a work package as completed, the report must explain and justify this). In this report, it needs to be detailed who did what (at the level of the participating organisations, not at the level of individual staff), indicating the contributions from beneficiaries.

Identification: (IQR_WPX_MX-MX)

Internally Quarterly Report responsible:

Reporting period:

Aims & Objectives of activities undertaken during the Quarter.

Please describe the aims and the objectives of the activities undertaken during the quarter framed in the corresponding tasks, in order to deliver the final output (corresponding deliverable).

Table 16 - Aims & Objectives of activities undertaken during the Quarter

1-3 months	Task 2.1. Identification & compilation of CE projects/initiatives M1-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL.	
	Task 2.2. Identification of further user-friendly CE resources M1-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL	
	Task 2.3. Analysis of CE projects/initiatives and identification of good practices M3-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL	
	Task 2.4. Identification and analysis of cross-sectorial and sectorial enabling technologies M3-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL.	
	Task 2.5. CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB platform development M1-M18 Leader INV, contributors ALL	

	Subtask 2.5.1. Gap analysis (M1-M4) Leader INV, contributors ALL	
	Subtask 2.5.2. Raw data specification (M1 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.	
	Subtask 2.5.3. Data organization and transformation (M1 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.	
	Subtask 2.5.4. User interface and experience design (M6 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.	

Activities undertaken & partners involved during the reporting period

Please provide a comprehensive overview of the activities undertaken and the partners involved throughout the reporting quarter in the pursuit of achieving the corresponding results (milestones & deliverables). Stress the proper implementation of the action as compared to the work described in the description of action (Annex 1).

Table 17 - Activities undertaken & partners involved during the reporting period

1-3 months	Task 2.1. Identification & compilation of CE projects/initiatives M1-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL.	
	Task 2.2. Identification of further user-friendly CE resources M1-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL	
	Task 2.3. Analysis of CE projects/initiatives and identification of good practices M3-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL	

Task 2.4. Identification and analysis of cross-sectorial and sectorial enabling technologies M3-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL.	
Task 2.5. CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB platform development M1-M18 Leader INV, contributors ALL	
<i>Subtask 2.5.1. Gap analysis (M1-M4) Leader INV, contributors ALL</i>	
<i>Subtask 2.5.2. Raw data specification (M1 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.</i>	
<i>Subtask 2.5.3. Data organization and transformation (M1 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.</i>	
<i>Subtask 2.5.4. User interface and experience design (M6 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.</i>	

Activities to be undertaken & partners involved during the next reporting period

Please describe next quarter's proposed **activities & partners** involved during the reporting period in order submit the corresponding deliverable on time and with the required quality.

4-6 months	Task 2.1. Identification & compilation of CE projects/initiatives M1-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL.	
	Task 2.2. Identification of further user-friendly CE resources M1-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL	
	Task 2.3. Analysis of CE projects/initiatives and identification of good practices M3-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL	
	Task 2.4. Identification and analysis of cross-sectorial and sectorial enabling technologies M3-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL.	
	Task 2.5. CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB platform development M1-M18 Leader INV, contributors ALL	
	<i>Subtask 2.5.1. Gap analysis (M1-M4) Leader INV, contributors ALL</i>	
	<i>Subtask 2.5.2. Raw data specification (M1 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.</i>	
	<i>Subtask 2.5.3. Data organization and transformation (M1 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.</i>	
	<i>Subtask 2.5.4. User interface and experience design (M6 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.</i>	

Issues arising during the quarter

Indicate changes in the WP action plan that might affect the corresponding deliverable submission. If the actions carried out have changed compared to the planned ones, a justification needs to be included here. Outline any change or corrective/contingency actions required.

Table 18 - Issues arising during the quarter

1-3	Task 2.1. Identification & compilation of CE	
-----	--	--

projects/initiatives M1-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL.	
Task 2.2. Identification of further user-friendly CE resources M1-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL	
Task 2.3. Analysis of CE projects/initiatives and identification of good practices M3-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL	
Task 2.4. Identification and analysis of cross-sectorial and sectorial enabling technologies M3-M18 Leader: CETEC, Contributors: ALL.	
Task 2.5. CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB platform development M1-M18 Leader INV, contributors ALL	
<i>Subtask 2.5.1. Gap analysis (M1-M4) Leader INV, contributors ALL</i>	
<i>Subtask 2.5.2. Raw data specification (M1 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.</i>	
<i>Subtask 2.5.3. Data organization and transformation (M1 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.</i>	
<i>Subtask 2.5.4. User interface and experience design (M6 – M18) Leader INV, contributors ALL.</i>	

Risk Identification and analysis

Please, if a risk related to this WP/ or its deliverables has been identified or has arisen during the quarter, it must be reported to the TASK 1.4 leader (UVEG) and included in

HE_K_CCRI_101135174 -

Documentos\03_WorkPackages\WP1_PM&Network_Coordination_I\T1_4_Internal_Evaluation\04_TecnicalWork

CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB WP1 RISK REGISTRY.xlsx

WP Milestone Status

Funded by
the European Union

Table 19 - Risk Identification and analysis (WP Milestone Status)

Guidelines/protocols for info gathering and analysis					Means of verification: The templates and the guidelines/protocols to gather the information developed under Task 2.1 are being used by partners. WP Leader will acknowledge the reception of it. Controllers: PC (KVC) & WP Leader (CETEC).				
10% <input type="checkbox"/>	20% <input type="checkbox"/>	30% <input type="checkbox"/>	40% <input type="checkbox"/>	50% <input type="checkbox"/>	60% <input type="checkbox"/>	70% <input type="checkbox"/>	80% <input type="checkbox"/>	90% <input type="checkbox"/>	100% <input type="checkbox"/>
Comments. Please describe the status of the milestone and define how the means of verification are being achieved:									

Decision on where to incorporate the platform taken and beta- version CCRI KNOWLEDGE HUB platform released					Means of verification: Platform set-up, in terms of it is working, and also a validation from the rest of the partners will be asked. Controllers: Coordination Team (KVC +CETEC)				
10% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	20% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	30% <input type="checkbox"/>	40% <input type="checkbox"/>	50% <input type="checkbox"/>	60% <input type="checkbox"/>	70% <input type="checkbox"/>	80% <input type="checkbox"/>	90% <input type="checkbox"/>	100% <input type="checkbox"/>
Comments. Please describe the status of the milestone and define how the means of verification are being achieved:									

Project Deliverables Status

Please, select the corresponding deliverable and mark the progress for the respective reporting quarter:

Deliverable Title: D2.1-CE projects/initiatives, GPs & less [CETEC | M17]

Table 20 - Project Deliverables Status

1. Definition of Deliverable (6%)	2. Planning (19%)	3. Research and Information Gathering (29%)	4. Design and Structuring(35%)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

- **Clearly define and fully understand the requirements of the deliverable.**
- **Establish goals and expected outcomes of the deliverable.**
- **Obtain approval and confirmation from involved partners regarding requirements and objectives.**
- Create a detailed plan including the schedule and necessary resources.
- Assign tasks and responsibilities to team members. Set milestones and checkpoints to assess progress.
- Identify and gather necessary information for the deliverable.
- Conduct research, surveys, or analyses as needed.
- Define the structure of the deliverable, including the table of contents.
- Create a detailed outline to guide the development of content.

5. Content Development (50%)	6. Review and Editing (60%)	7. Formatting and Presentation (65%)	8. Review Procedure & Final Approval (90%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write or develop the content of the deliverable according to the defined structure. • Review and ensure that the content is consistent and meets established requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct an internal review of the deliverable to correct grammatical and style errors. • Obtain feedback from the team and make necessary edits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply the appropriate format according to established guidelines & project templates. • Ensure visual presentation is consistent and professional. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform a final review of the deliverable to ensure quality and integrity following the review procedure set in the project. • Confirm that all requirements and objectives are met. • Obtain final approval from PC.
9. Submit Deliverable to Commission (100%)			
<input type="checkbox"/>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compile and submit the final deliverable to the Project Coordinator 			

Deliverable Title: D2.2-Resources compilation to support a successful transition to a circular economy in cities/regions (Folder with materials, tools and resources) [CETEC | M17]

Table 21 - Project Deliverables Status

1. Definition of Deliverable (6%)	2. Planning (19%)	3. Research and Information Gathering (29%)	4. Design and Structuring(35%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clearly define and fully understand the requirements of the deliverable. • Establish goals and expected outcomes of the deliverable. • Obtain approval and confirmation from involved partners regarding requirements and objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a detailed plan including the schedule and necessary resources. • Assign tasks and responsibilities to team members. Set milestones and checkpoints to assess progress. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and gather necessary information for the deliverable. • Conduct research, surveys, or analyses as needed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define the structure of the deliverable, including the table of contents. • Create a detailed outline to guide the development of content.
5. Content Development (50%)	6. Review and Editing (60%)	7. Formatting and Presentation (65%)	8. Review Procedure & Final Approval (90%)
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write or develop the content of the deliverable according to the defined structure. • Review and ensure that the content is consistent and meets established requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct an internal review of the deliverable to correct grammatical and style errors. • Obtain feedback from the team and make necessary edits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply the appropriate format according to established guidelines & project templates. • Ensure visual presentation is consistent and professional. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perform a final review of the deliverable to ensure quality and integrity following the review procedure set in the project. • Confirm that all requirements and objectives are met. • Obtain final approval from PC.
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9. Submit Deliverable to Commission (100%)

- **Compile and submit the final deliverable to the Project Coordinator**

Resources consumption monitoring

Please mark the resources used. This is only an estimate of the resources used to develop the activities corresponding to this WP.

Table 22 - Resources consumption monitoring

A. DIRECT PERSONNEL COSTS <i>(Person per months)</i>	C. DIRECT PURCHASE COSTS			D. OTHER COSTS CATEGORIES
	C1 Travel	C2 Equipment	C3 OGW&S	
0,00€	0,00€	0,00€	0,00€	0,00€
100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
90%	90%	90%	90%	90%
80%	80%	80%	80%	80%
70%	70%	70%	70%	70%
60%	60%	60%	60%	60%
50%	50%	50%	50%	50%
40%	40%	40%	40%	40%
30%	30%	30%	30%	30%
20%	20%	20%	20%	20%
10%	10%	10%	10%	10%

8.4. Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire

Section 1 - Well structured, logical and clear report

Table 23 - Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire (Section 1)

EQ1. Does the title page and opening pages provide key basic information?			
Name of deliverable			
WP related to the deliverable			
Name and organization(s) of deliverable author(s)			
The date of the review			
Table of contents			
List of acronyms			
EQ2. Executive Summary			
Question	Checklist	Remarks (justify checklist selection)	Page
(a) Is an Executive Summary included as part of the deliverable? If the answer is No, question (b) to (d) should be N/A.			
(b) Does the executive summary contain all the necessary elements? Necessary elements include all of the following: overview of the purpose, objectives and scope of the deliverable; intended audience; methodology; most important findings, conclusions and main recommendations where applicable.			
(c) Can the executive summary stand alone? It includes the main elements of the deliverable and should not introduce new information or arguments.			
(d) Can the executive summary inform decision			

<p>making? It should be short (ideally 1-3 pages) and increase the utility for decision makers by highlighting key priorities.</p>			
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Section 2: Purpose, Objectives and Scope

Table 24 - Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire (Section 2)

<p>2/ Are the deliverable's purpose, objectives and scope sufficiently clear?</p>			
<p>Question</p>	<p>Checklist</p>	<p>Remarks (justify checklist selection)</p>	<p>Page</p>
<p>EQ3. Is the purpose of the deliverable clear? This includes why the reported action is needed at this time, who needs the information, what information is needed, how the information will be used.</p>			
<p>EQ4. Are the objectives and scope of the deliverable clear and realistic? This includes the following: Objectives should be clear and explain what the reported action is seeking to achieve; Scope should clearly describe and justify what the reported action will and will not cover.</p>			
<p>EQ5. Do the objectives and scope relate to the purpose? The reasons for holding the action at this time in the project cycle (purpose) should link logically with the specific objectives the action seeks to achieve, and the boundaries chosen for the action (scope).</p>			

Section 3: Appropriate and sound methodology

Table 25 - Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire (Section 3)

3/ Is the methodology appropriate & sound?			
Question	Checklist	Remarks (justify checklist selection)	Page
EQ6. Does the deliverable specify the methodology used (data collection methods, analysis methods, sampling methods and benchmarks, or others)? This should include the rationale for selecting methods and their limitations based on commonly accepted best practice.			
EQ7. Does the deliverable specify data sources, the rationale for their selection, and their limitations? This should include a discussion of how the mix of data sources was used to obtain a diversity of perspectives, ensure accuracy and overcome data limits. If the action does not envisage collecting data, the answer should be N/A.			
EQ8. Are the levels and activities of stakeholder consultation described? This goes beyond just using stakeholders as sources of information and includes the degree of participation in the action itself. The deliverable should include the rationale for selecting this level of participation. Please consider the soundness of the description and rationale for the degree of participation rather than the level of participation itself.			
EQ9. Does the methodology answer the reported action questions in the context of the reported action? The methodology should link back to the Purpose and be capable of providing answers to the reported action questions.			

Section 4: Findings and Conclusions.

Table 26 - Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire (Section 4)

4/ Are the findings and conclusions, clearly presented, relevant and based on evidence & sound analysis?

Question	Checklist	Remarks (justify checklist selection)	Page
<p>EQ10. Are findings clearly presented and based on the objective use of the reported evidence? Findings on results should clearly distinguish outputs, outcomes and impacts (where appropriate). Findings must demonstrate full marshalling and objective use of the evidence generated. Findings should also tell the 'whole story' of the evidence and avoid bias.</p>			
<p>EQ11. Do the findings address all of the reported action's stated purpose and objectives? The findings should seek to systematically address all of the stated purpose and objectives according to the planned framework articulated in the deliverable.</p>			
<p>EQ12. Do findings demonstrate the progression to results based on the evidence reported? There should be a logical chain developed by the findings, which show the progression (or lack of) from implementation to results.</p>			
<p>EQ13. Are gaps and limitations discussed? The findings may be inadequate to answer all the reported action questions as satisfactorily as intended, in this case the limitations should be clearly presented and discussed. Any gaps in the action or unintended effects should also be</p>			

addressed.			
EQ14. Are unexpected findings discussed? If the evidence reveals (or suggests) unusual or unexpected issues, these should be highlighted and discussed in terms of their implications.			
EQ15. Do the conclusions present both the strengths and weaknesses of the results? Conclusions should give a balanced view of both the stronger aspects and weaker aspects of the results with reference to the purpose.			
EQ16. Do the conclusions represent actual insights into important issues that add value to the findings? Conclusions should go beyond findings and identify important underlying problems and/or priority issues. Simple conclusions that are already well known do not add value and should be avoided.			
EQ17. Are the conclusions pitched at a level that is relevant to the end users? Conclusions should speak to the project participants, stakeholders and users. These may cover a wide range of groups and conclusions should thus be stated clearly and accessibly: adding value and understanding to the deliverable (for example, some stakeholders may not understand the methodology or findings, but the conclusions should clarify what			

these findings mean to them in the context of the action).			
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Section 5: Overall structure and coherence.

Table 27 - Deliverable Quality Evaluation Questionnaire (Section 5)

Item	Answer (Y/N)
Does the deliverable comply with the format provided by the partner in charge of communication and dissemination, including project logo, project code, deliverable name, date and logo of the funding agency?	
Is the deliverable written in appropriate and accurate language, with correct grammar and spelling?	
Is the deliverable written in a clear and understandable way? Is the language appropriate for the target audience? Is unnecessary technical jargon avoided?	
Is the deliverable well structured, with ideas and arguments presented in a logical and coherent way that facilitates the reader's understanding?	

8.5. Checklist for scientific dissemination outputs

Table 28 - Checklist for scientific dissemination outputs

QC dimension	Expert opinion (1 Very Low; -5 Very High)	Rationale
Thematic relevance, related to the journal or congress in which it will be published.		
High level of proficiency in the topic.		
Clarity of the exposition.		
Originality and importance of the scientific output within the context of the research in this field and the state of the art.		

Consistency in the line of argument as regards the foundation of the key theoretical approaches.		
Robustness in the evidence selected and rigour in the revision of sources and cited references. References from recognised and specialised sources. Recent sources.		
Rigorous and sound methodology. Appropriateness and relevance of methods used.		
Correspondence between methodology and objectives.		
Correspondence between methodology and theoretical foundation.		
Correlation between the discussion and the conclusions.		

8.6. Transnational Meeting Quality Evaluation Questionnaire

Table 29 - Transnational Meeting Quality Evaluation Questionnaire

Items	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1. Relevance and Purpose of the Meeting					
1.1. The purpose of the meeting was clearly defined and communicated to all participants.	1	2	3	4	5
1.2. The topics discussed at the meeting were relevant to the objectives of the project.	1	2	3	4	5
2. Preparation and Organisation					
2.1. Participants were provided with the necessary information to	1	2	3	4	5

prepare for the meeting well in advance.					
2.2. The meeting was organised efficiently and effectively.	1	2	3	4	5
2.3. The scheduled time of the meeting was respected.	1	2	3	4	5
2.4. The meeting facilities were adequate and well equipped for the needs of the meeting.	1	2	3	4	5
3. Participation					
3.1. All participants had the opportunity to actively contribute to the discussion.	1	2	3	4	5
3.2. The meeting promoted an atmosphere of respect and collaboration.	1	2	3	4	5
4. Communication and Clarity					
4.1. Speakers communicated their points in a clear and understandable manner.	1	2	3	4	5
4.2. Sufficient time was provided for questions and discussion after each presentation.	1	2	3	4	5
5. Results of the Meeting					
5.1. The objectives of the meeting were achieved.	1	2	3	4	5
5.2. Clear decisions were taken and responsibilities were assigned for further action.	1	2	3	4	5
6. Added value					
6.1. The meeting brought value to the project and its objectives.	1	2	3	4	5
6.2. Lessons learned or best practices were identified during the meeting that could be useful for the future.	1	2	3	4	5

8.7. Internal Evaluation Survey for the project internal quality

Table 30 - Internal Evaluation Survey for the project internal quality

Items	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
1. Planning and Objective Definition					
1.1. The project's objectives are clearly defined and communicated to all team members.	1	2	3	4	5
2. Coordination and Delegation					
2.1. Responsibilities and tasks are clearly distributed among team members.	1	2	3	4	5
2.2. Team members receive constant feedback on their performance.	1	2	3	4	5
2.3. Changes in task distribution are effectively managed.	1	2	3	4	5
3. Communication and Transparency					
3.1. There is effective and open communication among team members.	1	2	3	4	5
3.2. Regular updates on the project's progress are shared.	1	2	3	4	5
3.3. The project coordinators clearly and effectively communicate expectations and changes.	1	2	3	4	5
3.4. The project coordinators provide constructive and timely feedback to team members.	1	2	3	4	5
4. Problem-solving					
4.1. Problems and obstacles are addressed in a timely and efficient manner.	1	2	3	4	5
4.2. Collaboration among the team to solve problems is encouraged.	1	2	3	4	5
5. Evaluation and Continuous Improvement					

5.1. There are methods for evaluating the progress and success of the project.	1	2	3	4	5
5.2. Opportunities for improvement are identified and implemented throughout the project.	1	2	3	4	5
5.3. The project coordinators and the partners specifically tasked with it regularly evaluate team performance and progress.	1	2	3	4	5
5.4. The project coordinators encourage the growth and development of team members.	1	2	3	4	5
6. Added value					
6.1. The project coordination adds value to the project and its objectives.	1	2	3	4	5
6.2. Lessons learned or best practices are identified during the project that could be useful for the future.	1	2	3	4	5
7. Leadership and Management					
7.1. The project coordinators demonstrate a solid understanding of the project's objectives.	1	2	3	4	5
7.2. The project coordinators show effective decision-making skills.	1	2	3	4	5
7.3. The project coordinators are able to motivate and keep the team engaged.	1	2	3	4	5
7.4. The project coordinators handle conflicts and difficulties efficiently.	1	2	3	4	5
8. Coordination and Organisation					
8.1. The project coordinators efficiently coordinate and organise tasks and responsibilities.	1	2	3	4	5
8.2. The project coordinators ensure that delivery deadlines are met.	1	2	3	4	5

8.3. The project coordinators maintain efficient planning and scheduling.	1	2	3	4	5
9. Communication and Dissemination					
9.1 A comprehensive Dissemination and Communication Strategy has been developed and communicated to all partners.					
9.2 Project materials such as flyers, videos, news releases, and monthly specials are created and distributed in a timely manner.					
9.3 I am satisfied with my involvement in the project's communication and dissemination activities.					
10. Self-Assessment					
10.1. I am generally satisfied with the way the project is progressing					
10.2. I think the project is achieving its objectives satisfactorily.					
10.3. I believe that the project will achieve a high level of impact.					

